

Creating a Measurement Scheduler for Automated Operation of the Radio Spectrum Measurement System

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Abstract: Limited time, funding, and personnel resources require that spectrum surveys be performed with maximum efficiency. This paper describes an approach taken to achieve this high efficiency: the automation of time intensive measurements that are performed on a regular basis. Organizations that are responsible for spectrum management periodically require spectrum surveys to identify spectrum usage and compatibility issues. The Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS) has developed an automated scheduler to reduce the need for highly trained personnel on-site and to collect/record data on a 24-hour basis. This paper details the development and implementation of the scheduler, including future plans for its enhancement.

INTRODUCTION

Agencies responsible for spectrum management (such as radio range management, test range frequency management, cellular management, naval frequency management, etc.) periodically need to assess spectrum usage and compatibility issues. For example, a cellular provider may be interested in assessing the peak versus off-peak frequency band usage to determine channel availability and assess the need for additional base stations. Naval frequency management organizations may need to identify intermittent sources of spectrum interference that could hinder mission critical communications. Radio range management organizations may wish to determine how safety channels (police, medical, etc.) are affected during national events (such as the Olympic Games). In all scenarios, comprehensive, 24-hour, multi-week spectrum surveys may be required to adequately characterize relevant spectrum usage. Especially with intermittent interface sources, the longer a survey is performed the greater the probability that interference will be detected.

For the Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS), the research and engineering arm for the U.S. Department of Commerce, spectrum surveys are initiated by the National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA). NTIA is responsible for managing the Federal Government's use of the radio spectrum and has requested spectrum surveys at a variety of sites, which recently include Atlanta [1], Los Angeles [2], San Diego [3], and Denver [4]. The Atlanta survey was performed to identify the effect of spectrum congestion before, during, and after the 1996 Olympic Games.

The other surveys characterized spectrum usage patterns in large metropolitan areas.

Usually spectrum surveys are performed for multiple frequency bands, across wide frequency ranges. To perform comprehensive spectrum surveys ITS designed and developed the Radio Spectrum Measurement System (RSMS). Among other functions, the RSMS uses ITS custom designed algorithms to measure radio signals at various sites. Since the data collected during measurement surveys are usually quite extensive (data from a one to two week period), the measurement results must be organized and recorded in a logical order. Ideally these jobs would be accomplished without extensive personnel deployments. To meet these requirements, ITS has created a measurement scheduler that automatically executes scheduled measurements on a 24-hour basis, and catalogs the results in measurement log files.

Although ITS has performed automated scheduled measurements for twenty years, the previous scheduling systems have been rather basic (the current system is an old DOS entry line system). To take advantage of new technology and the latest programming languages that include built in GUI capability, the ITS scheduler has been redesigned. The new version contains a variety of new features; for example the original system limited the number of scheduled measurements to 64, whereas in the new system the number is essentially unlimited.

No commercial schedulers are available which will meet ITS needs. The ITS scheduler has the advantage of being able to incorporate each of these specialized measurements into a comprehensive tool. Also, by designing a customized measurement scheduler, ITS can easily add features or change functionality as desired.

THE RSMS

The RSMS is a complete measurement system that was designed and developed by ITS. The RSMS contains spectrum-monitoring equipment integrated into a mobile vehicle that can easily be deployed as needed to sites throughout the United States. An antenna is mounted above the vehicle on a telescoping mast that can be raised and rotated to enhance the signal reception. A control computer within the

vehicle uses a general-purpose interface bus (GPIB) to control the measurement equipment and to perform automated measurements.

Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the RSMS hardware. An antenna system at the top of a telescoping and rotating tower provides a selection of omni and directional antennas across a wide frequency range. Signals pass through an ITS-designed 2-18 GHz preselector, where signals are filtered and amplified, before passing through a coaxial cable running down the antenna tower. A signal passes into the van, through the RF system controller, where extra amplification is provided for

signals in the 2-18 GHz range to compensate for the additional RF losses in the tower coaxial cable. The signal passes through the 20 Hz - 2 GHz preselector, which provides tracking preselection and preamplification for signals below 2 GHz. Finally, the signal enters the spectrum analyzer, which provides a wide range of spectrum measurement capabilities. A digital oscilloscope is available for measurements requiring high-resolution time-domain analysis. The antenna controller is a touch-screen computer that allows programmatic or manual control of the ITS 2-18 GHz Preselector. A GPS system provides accurate time, date, and location - which is recorded as part of the supporting data for each measurement.

Figure 1. Hardware Block Diagram For The Primary RSMS Equipment.

To automate the suite of measurements within the RSMS, a measurement control system (MCS) was created. Using computer control, the MCS programmatically calibrates the system, collects data on the hardware, downloads the data to the computer, processes the data, creates/prints standardized reports [5], and saves the data to files on the computer. The current MCS library of "canned measurements" contains programs for the following measurements (automated calibration can be performed before each measurement if desired): radiation hazard, secondary and primary radar pulse repetition frequency, stepped measurement [6], single or multiple frequency swept measurement, primary and secondary [7] radar antenna pattern measurement, spectrum signature [8], and spectragraph. These measurements typically combine functionality from several pieces of equipment and require extensive signal processing.

SCHEDULER DESIGN CRITERIA

The canned MCS measurements produce accurate and standardized measurement with minimal user input. The user selects an MCS canned routine, accepts (or edits) default measurement parameters, starts the measurement, responds to error/user messages that appear on the screen during the measurement, and records/prints a data file with measurement results and supporting logistics information. The scheduler was designed to permit a series of canned MCS measurements to be accomplished as above, but completely without user intervention. Initially, ITS incorporated the MCS canned routines for the swept frequency and stepped frequency measurements into the scheduler, since combinations of these two measurements are used extensively in long-term spectrum monitoring.

The scheduler has two modes of operation: schedule creation and schedule execution. The creation mode includes retrieving, editing, printing, and saving the schedule. The execution mode automatically performs the measurements in the schedule and includes an automatic save to a data file after each successful measurement. Figure 2 shows a block diagram of the scheduler functionality.

Figure 2. Scheduler Block Diagram.

Included in the editing portion of the creation mode, as shown in the top menus of Figure 3, are many spreadsheet-like functions. The user is able to delete, cut, copy, paste, insert, clear, and modify measurement data. Each time an editing function is performed, an extensive amount of data is manipulated, including the number that uniquely identifies the measurement, the type of measurement, the set of measurement input parameters, and the measurement comments (see the data in Figure 3 – the event number, time interval, and measurement identification will be implemented in a future version of the scheduler).

As long as at least one measurement exists in the schedule, the user can enter from any stage in the creation mode to the beginning step of the execution mode. During the execution mode, each scheduled measurement is automatically performed and the data from successful measurements is saved. The user indicates the number of iterations of the schedule to be initiated, or chooses indefinite execution, where user interaction is required to stop the schedule. Any measurement error will cause the current measurement to terminate, but does not affect the other scheduled measurements. However, if *all* of the scheduled measurements produce errors, then the scheduler will halt and the user will be notified. The errors and messages that would normally appear to the user are recorded in the scheduler log file.

During the execution mode, the user can observe the status of the measurement (shown in Figure 4) and can interrupt the schedule to return to the schedule creation mode to add/change measurements. When the user returns to the execution mode, the schedule does not restart at the first measurement, but continues on the current measurement (or the next available if the current measurement was deleted). In this way, the user has maximum flexibility to change the measurements as signals of interest are discovered, such as an unexpected interference signal that requires investigation.

SCHEDULER DESIGN IMPLEMENTATION

The scheduler was implemented using a main software screen, shown in Figure 3, and a status screen, shown in Figure 4. The main screen, Figure 3, is used for both the schedule creation and to begin the schedule execution mode. The status screen, in Figure 4, shows the user the schedule status during execution mode. The status screen displays the current measurement number, iteration number, data file number, the record number within the data file, number of scheduler errors (either from saving the data or running the measurement), and the number of file errors (only errors from saving the data).

The arrows pointing to the menus above Figure 3 show the ITS drop-down menu choices available at the top of the main scheduler screen. Both the "schedule" and "measurement" drop-down menus are used during the schedule creation mode. The schedule menu allows the user to perform functions that

relate to the entire schedule (e.g. opening a schedule, saving a schedule). The measurement menu allows the user to perform

functions on the individual measurements in the schedule (e.g. editing a measurement, deleting a measurement).

Schedule		Measurement	
Open	Ctrl+O	Edit	Ctrl+E
Clear	Ctrl+W	Cut	Ctrl+X
Save	Ctrl+S	Copy	Ctrl+C
Print		Paste	Ctrl+V
Delete		Insert	Ctrl+R
		Clear	Ctrl+L
		Delete	Ctrl+D

As previously discussed, extensive measurement information is contained in each row of the schedule, as shown in Figure 3. In addition to the measurement number and type of measurement (stepped or swept), each row contains an entire set of measurement input parameters and measurement comments. Due to space constraints, to view the entire row of values, the user must use the scroll bar. However, if the user scrolls to the end of the table, the beginning of the table is no longer visible. Therefore, as a convenience to the user, ITS added "Meas. Parameters" and "Meas. Comments" which show the parameter values and the comments, respectively, for the selected row in the schedule. In Figure 3 the parameters and comments are shown for the first row, since that row is currently selected.

Figure 3. The Main Scheduler Software Screen.

Figure 4. The Scheduler Status Screen.

Once the user has entered all measurements into the schedule (for example, three measurements in Figure 3), the user presses "start" and the scheduler enters into execution mode. During execution mode each of the measurements will be executed automatically, with user specified parameters, and the data will automatically be saved to file. Figure 5 shows an example execution of the first (stepped) measurement and Figure 6 shows an example execution of the second (swept) measurement, from the schedule in Figure 3. The stepped measurement steps through frequencies, obtaining one value from each time trace (generally the user selects the maximum values). The swept measurement collects multiple sweeps across a frequency band and tabulates the minimum, maximum, and mean data values for each frequency. Both measurements allow capabilities that are not customarily available on standard hardware alone. For example, the stepped measurement automatically adjusts input attenuation at each frequency step, increasing the dynamic range of the measurement system.

The number of schedule iterations indicates how many times the entire set of measurements will be executed. In the example in Figure 3, this number is set to 0, which indicates an infinite number of executions (i.e., execution will continue until we get all errors in one iteration or until the user chooses to stop). After each measurement is complete, either an error message or a success message is written to a user selected log

file. In either case, pertinent information about the measurement is recorded on each line of the log file.

The status screen, in Figure 4, is used to show the status during the schedule execution mode. During execution, as each measurement in the schedule is performed, measurement screens appear, hiding the main schedule screen from the user. The smaller status screen, which is always the top-most screen, allows the user to view the schedule status at all times. The status screen is constantly updated as measurements complete and the results are saved to files. The user can press the "stop" button on the status window to terminate the schedule at any time. During these schedule interruptions, the user can edit the schedule before continuing with the scheduled execution or the user can exit from the schedule altogether.

CONCLUSION

ITS has implemented scheduler software that automates the execution of the stepped and swept measurements. These measurements were chosen since they are widely used for long term RSMS operation of assessing spectrum utilization and identifying spectrum compatibility issues. The scheduler allows spectrum management organizations to perform twenty-four hour, multiple week monitoring and to create accurate, organized, and efficient measurement surveys.

Figure 5. An Example Of An Automated Execution Of The Stepped Measurement.

Figure 6. An Example Of An Automated Execution Of The Swept Measurement.

Program status reviews at ITS have identified three primary enhancement possibilities for the scheduler. First, the remaining seven MCS measurements could be incorporated into the scheduler. Also, since certain measurements are utilized frequently, it would be time efficient to save a library of measurements for convenient retrieval. Finally, a remote control capability would add efficiency and flexibility. Generally, ITS engineers travel to a measurement site to observe the RSMS in operation. During these measurements, ITS engineers usually need only to make minor modifications to the schedule. If the engineers could operate the schedule, save the schedule, retrieve the data, and process the data remotely, the measurements could be performed more efficiently and monitored by a technician. Also, reports could be generated more quickly (perhaps even before the measurement vehicle has returned from the field).

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Sanders, G. Hand, and V. Lawrence, "Land Mobile Radio Channel Usage Measurements at the 1996 Summer Olympic Games", NTIA Report 98-357, September 1998.
- [2] F. Sanders, B. Ramsey, and V. Lawrence, "Broadband Spectrum Survey at Los Angeles, California", NTIA Report 97-336, May, 1997.
- [3] F. Sanders, B. Ramsey, and V. Lawrence, "Broadband Spectrum Survey at San Diego, California", NTIA Report 97-334, December, 1996.
- [4] F. Sanders, and V. Lawrence, "Broadband Spectrum Survey at Denver, Colorado", NTIA Report 95-321, September, 1995.
- [5] S. Davidson, "Standard and Comparable Measurements Using LabView®", in Proc. NI Week 98, Austin, TX, August, 1998.
- [6] R. Chambliss, "Automating Measurement of RF Spectra from an Operating Radar", in Proc. NI Week 97, Austin, TX, August, 1997.
- [7] J. Kub, "Using LabView® to Characterize the Air Traffic Control Radar Beacon System", in Proc. NI Week 97, Austin, TX, August, 1997.
- [8] T. Sparkman, "Characterizing U.S. Airport Emitters Using the Radio Frequency Interference Monitoring System and LabView®", in Proc. NI Week 98, Austin, TX, August, 1998.